

Preliminary research on potential raw material sources for dolomitic lime mortars at St. John's convent at Müstair, Switzerland

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Abstract

The Benedictine convent of St. John at Müstair (UNESCO world heritage site) in Grisons, Switzerland, preserves a huge amount of well-documented (dolomitic) archaeological mortar samples dated from the Carolingian to the Baroque Age (8th to 18th century). In the medieval period, the architecture of the Val Müstair and the surrounding regions was characterized by stone and mortar constructions. The geological overview of the area around the monastery indicates that dolomitic rocks are widely available and the production of lime was a common practice in the Müstair valley as demonstrated by the presence of mortar mixers, lime-kilns and local toponyms.

As part of an ongoing research project, the question about the potential source(s) of the raw materials for the production of the binder of the historic mortars was posed. The proposed research is based on the close relationship between the geological raw materials and the underburnt relics (lime lumps) found in the archaeological mortars.

Textural features and mineralogical composition were investigated by combining Polarizing Light Microscopy (PLM) and X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD) analysis.

Results indicate that the textural evidence (sometimes) retained by underburnt relics of dolomitic rocks cannot be used as possible criteria for provenance studies due to the high variability of dolomite crystal size, fabric and heterogeneity within the same group and at the scale of individual samples. However, the presence of silicate phases may suggest potential proxies.

1. Introduction

The monastic site of St. John in the Swiss canton of Grisons was founded in the last quarter of the 8th century. The complex then underwent significant changes, and most of the original complex was subsequently replaced by newer structures. Thanks to decades of archaeological research at the site, the construction history of the monastery is well-known [1]. Over the centuries, buildings were torn down and new ones added, so that today the site preserves structures from across 12 centuries, dated from around 775 AD to the present. Since the beginning of research activities at the site in 1969, over 5000 mortar samples from all construction periods have been collected. This provides a unique basis for the study of historic mortar production and building techniques. Since 2017 the project “Mortar Technology and Construction History at Müstair Monastery”¹ has been looking at these questions by applying an interdisciplinary approach to the study of the site, its mortar samples and construction history, as well as the region around it.

The ongoing research project offered the possibility for an in-depth study of the raw materials used for the design of the mixes used in mortar production through the centuries, focusing on the provenance of those used for lime production. There is evidence of the use of dolomitic lime in Carolingian mortars [2, 3] and painted Romanesque plasters [4]; in addition, the presence of dolomitic rock formations very close to the monastery sets ideal conditions for such research.

Provenance studies are based on the textural and mineralogical relationship between raw materials used for lime production and underburnt relics (lime inclusions or lime lumps) in archaeological mortars. Petrographic examination of lime inclusions in historic mortars from Scotland and Belgium [5] provided clues for the limestone provenance thanks to the presence of relics or pseudomorph textures of the original rock. In addition, underburnt fragments may also provide information about the hydraulicity of

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the lime as for the Notre-Dame Cathedral in Tournai, Belgium [6-7]. The use of marble for quicklime production used for the Leaning Tower of Pisa, Italy [8], is assumed on the basis of the close vicinity and availability of quarries, even if no textural and geochemical data support this evidence. The vicinity of limestone sources and the presence of a fragment of raw material in the thin section are the only (weak) arguments for demonstrating the provenance of ancient Indian lime [9]. The proximity of the limestone outcrop is the criterion for assessing the provenance of the carbonate raw materials used for the mortars and plasters of the Roman villa in ancient Stabiae in Naples, Italy [10]. The presence of tufa fragments in Roman mortars collected from several places in La Rioja, Spain [11] is advocated as possible raw material evidence for making lime. Finally, the provenance of raw materials for dolomitic and calcitic lime production in the post-Cistercian abbey in Kamieniec Ząbłowski (Poland) was inferred combining archival, historical, geological and petrographic evidence [12].

The aims of this manuscript are the following: i. to investigate the possibility to make a clear distinction between the diverse dolomitic rock groups outcropping in Müstair valley on the basis of their specific textural characteristics and fabric features; ii. to correlate the petrographic features of the raw materials with those of the lime inclusions found in the archaeological mortars; iii. to understand the role that accompanying minerals could play as distinctive (silicate) phases; iv. to identify toponyms referring to lime-burning activities in the Müstair valley and correlate them with potential quarrying sites.

2. Geographic and geological overview of the area

The Münstertal (Convent Valley) lies within the domain of the Austroalpine nappes, in the southeast of the Swiss canton of Grisons, in close proximity to the border with Italy (figure 1). The valley is oriented approximately from west to east and is traversed by the Rom stream. Its most important tributaries are the streams Aua da Vau (which descends through the Val Vau), Muranzina (Val Muraunza) and the Valgarola (Val d'Avigna). The first two tributaries flow from the south and southwest, while the third comes from the north. Behind the Val Vau there is another valley easily accessible from the Müstair

valley, the Val Mora, but the stream running through it, the Aua da Val Mora, empties northwards into the Inn river.

The area North of Val Mora, Val Vau and the lower Val Müstair basically is composed of Permo-Triassic sediments from the S-Charl-Nappe and their basement, the Sesvenna and Müntertal crystalline. The southern chain area concerning Piz Murtaröl, Piz Schumbraida, Piz Umbrail, Piz Chavalatsch, is characterized by several thrust nappes, the Quattervals and Umbrail nappes made of mainly dolomitic rocks and the Chavalatsch nappe made of crystalline rocks [13].

Orler	Quatterval- Umbrail	S-charl- Sesvenna	Terza-Müntet	Chavalatsch	
					Obere Trias
					Mittl.-unt. Trias
	Quartär i.a.			W.-V. Maranza-E	Verrucano
	Sackungen z.T.				Kristallin
	Überschiebung		Abschiebung		Bruch
	Düsserandond-Abschiebung		Gallo-Ab- oder Überschiebung		Trupchun-Überschiebung

Figure 1. Schematic geological view of Müstair valley (by Trümpy, 2007). Capital letters from C to I indicate the geological sampling areas; c1-c4 notations the historical lime-kilns (CH Piz Chavalatsch; CO Piz Costainas; CU Cuclèr da Jon dad’Onsch; DA Piz Daint; LA Piz Lad; MB Munt da la Bescha; MU Piz Murtaröl; SB Piz Schumbraida; TU Piz Turettas; TZ Piz Terza/Urtirolaspitz; UM Piz Umbrail; am Alp Mora; av Val d’Avigna; fr Fradetssch; Ir Lai da Rims; mi Minschuns; mt Müntet; of Ofenpass; pu Pass Umbrail; tr Taunter Ruinas; va Vallatscha; vr Val Ruina; vv Val vau. † S. J. St. John’s Monastery).

3. Materials and methods

Potential quarrying sites and historical locations of lime kilns were identified by studying the geological and topographical maps of the Swiss Federal office of Topography and then carrying out field surveys. The toponym “chalchera” in the official cadastral surveying plans was used as an indicator for the locations of historical lime kilns. In order to qualify as a potential quarrying site, dolomitic rock outcrops had to be easily accessible by path or road. The sites were then compared to the locations of potential quarrying sites, in order to determine methods of selection and transport of raw materials.

Samples of dolomitic rocks were collected in the southern and northern sector of Münstertal, corresponding to the Upper Austroalpine domain (*Engadiner Dolomiten*). The places where samples come from are reported in figure 1 and a description is provided in Table 1, including the analytical techniques used.

Table 1. Geological and archaeological samples description

GEOLOGICAL SAMPLES					
ID	Location	Description	Notes	Analytical techniques	
				PLM	XRPD
C	Val Vau	Pebbles and gravels from the river bed deriving from the weathering of the southern dolomitic rock mountains	A (restored) lime-kiln is in the same area (Valchava; c3 in figure 1)	✓	✓
D	Ofenpass	(Isolated) dolomitic rock outcrops	=	✓	✓
E		Dolomitic rocks associated with gypsum	=	✓	✓
F	Piz Umbrail	Slope detrital fragments	Dark dolomite	✓	✓
G		Individual samples taken from an outcropping area	Yellowish-brown dolomite	✓	✓
I	Lü village	Samples from layered sequences	Topographic sheet reports here a place called lime-kiln (<i>chalchera</i> ; c2 in figure 1)	✓	✓
ARCHAEOLOGICAL SAMPLES					
ID	Location	Description	Notes	Analytical techniques	
				PLM	XRPD

6577	Carolingian mortars	Binder		✓
315, 11902		Mortar	✓	
8641	Ottonian mortars	Binder		✓
		Mortar	✓	
24351	Early Romanesque mortars	Binder		✓
24318, 24351		Mortar	✓	
13112	Late Romanesque mortars	Binder		✓
3340, 22570		Mortar	✓	
23604	Gothic mortars	Binder		✓
2137, 23276		Mortar	✓	

Mortars of different periods were selected and their binders analysed in order to detect the nature of mineralogical phases correlated with dolomitic raw materials.

The binder of the archaeological mortars was separated by sieving. The samples were broken in a plastic bag using nipper pieces to avoid fine splinter of the aggregate. The crushed material was vibrated in a sieve series. The grain-size fraction <63 μm was chosen for all the samples, except the sample 6577 (fraction <45 μm).

The mineralogical analysis of the mortar binders and of geological samples was carried out using X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD). After grinding in an agate mortar, randomly oriented samples were prepared and deposited in the hollow of a Si monocrystal zero-background plate, supplied by Assing spa, Monterotondo, Italy. A Rigaku Miniflex system, operating in $\theta:2\theta$ mode was used; generator setting 30 kV, 10 mA, Cu anode (Cu $K\alpha = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$), Ni filter, 2θ range $5-55^\circ$, step size 0.02° , scan speed $0.3^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$. Qualitative phase determination was carried out using the software QualX2.0 [14] and the correlated COD database [15].

Polarized Light Microscopy (PLM) on thin sections of (archaeological and geological samples; except sample C-04 which requires thin section preparation using staining techniques) was carried out for mineralogical and textural analysis; a Zeiss Axioskop 4.0 Polarizing Light Microscope (PLM) was used and micrographs were acquired with a digital camera, and processed with the software Axiovision (Zeiss, release 4.5.1).

4. Results

4.1 X-ray powder Diffraction (XRPD)

4.1.1 Geological samples

Qualitative mineralogical analysis of dolomitic rock samples is reported in Table 2A. All of the samples are carbonate rocks composed of dolomite, generally with accompanying minerals.

According to the mineralogical analysis, the samples belonging to the D and I groups exhibit not negligible amount of quartz. This mineral is absent in the sample groups F and C (except sample C-03) and in traces in the group G. Group E is characterized by the presence of gypsum (Gp). Illite/muscovite (Ill/Ms) is a mineral always associated with the I sequence. It was also detected in the samples D-03 and G-01. Finally, barite (Brt) was identified in the sample G-02.

Table 2A. Qualitative mineralogical analysis of rock samples (*)

ID	Qualitative mineralogical analysis					
	Dol	Cal	Qz	Ill/Ms	Gp	Brt
C-01	+++					
C-02	+++					
C-03	+++		tr			
C-04	+++	+++				
C-06	+++					
D-01	+++		+			
D-02	+++		tr			
D-03	+++	+	+	+		
E-Dol	+++		tr		+	
F-01	+++					
F-02	+++					
G-01	+++		tr	+		
G-02	+++		tr			tr
I1-01	+++	tr	+	tr		
I1-02l	+++	tr	+	tr		
I1-02u	+++		+	+		
I1-03	+++	tr	+	tr		
I2-01	+++	tr	+	tr		
I2-02	+++	tr	+	tr		

(*) Notation used: +++ mineral in predominant relative amount; ++ subordinate; + accessory; tr trace; - absent or below the limit of detection. Mineral abbreviations as in Whitney and Evans [16].

4.1.2 Archaeological samples

Qualitative mineralogical analysis of the binder of the archaeological samples is reported in Table 2B. Results indicate that the binder of the samples 6577 and 24351 is dolomitic for the presence of hydromagnesite. The presence of amorphous phases (related with the formation of Mg-based products?) was detected in the samples 8641 and 23604. The remaining sample (13112) does not display any mineralogical phase related with the carbonation of dolomitic lime. The presence of clay minerals, quartz and dolomite is due to the fraction of aggregates that passed the sieve (grain size <63 µm). For the same reason, Fe-oxides (most probably both goethite and hematite, respectively Gth and Hem in Table 2B) were found as constituents of the sample 24351 (the binder of this sample is pale brown).

Table 2B. Qualitative mineralogical analysis of the binder of archaeological mortars (*)

ID	Qualitative mineralogical analysis								
	Cal	Qz	Dol	Ill/Ms	Chl	(H)Mgs	Gth	Hem	Amorphous
6577	++	+++		+		tr			
8641	+++	+	tr	tr	tr				✓
24351	+++	++	+	+	tr	tr	tr	tr	
13112	++	+++	tr	tr	tr				
23604	+	+++	+	tr	tr				✓

(*) Notation used: +++ mineral in predominant relative amount; ++ subordinate; + accessory; tr trace; - absent or below the limit of detection. Mineral abbreviations as in Whitney and Evans [12].

4.2 Polarizing Light Microscopy (PLM)

4.2.1 Geological samples

The petrography of the dolomite rock samples is reported in Table 3. The dolomitic rock texture was described according to their crystal boundary shapes, size and shape of dolomite crystals [17].

Table 3. Petrographic analysis of dolomite rock samples

SAMPLE ID	MINERALOGY	TEXTURE AND OTHER FEATURES
C01-C06	Dolomite	Equigranular non planar dolomite with void filling planar-e dolomite crystals
C-02	Dolomite	very fine (peloidal) dolomite with non mimic replacement of bioclasts
C-03	Dolomite, quartz	very fine; matrix replaced by (inequigranular) non planar dolomite with void filling non planar dolomite and quartz crystals
D01-D02	Dolomite	fine; void filling non planar dolomite
D03	Dolomite	(equigranular) non planar
E-Dol	Dolomite, opaque minerals	very fine with replaced microcrystalline equigranular (planar-s) dolomite cement. (Inequigranular) non planar and planar-s void filling dolomite occurs. Presence of dark stylolites
F-01	Dolomite	(equigranular) non planar; presence of dark stylolites
F-02	Dolomite	very fine and microcrystalline with replaced inequigranular planar-s cement. Presence of dark stylolites
G-01	Dolomite; Fe-oxides	Microcrystalline, non planar; presence of dark microlaminations
G-02	Dolomite, quartz, (yellow) Fe-oxyhydroxides	(equigranular) non planar
I1-01, I1-02l, I1-02u, I1-03	Dolomite, quartz, illite/muscovite	microcrystalline (equigranular) with void filling
I2-01, I2-02		

The petrographic examination of the dolomitic rocks analysed indicates the variability of the textural characteristics both between the different groups and within the individual group (figure 2). In addition, there is evidence of textural variability at the scale of individual samples. The sequences I1 and I2 display very similar textural features. More promising is the presence of accompanying minerals scattered within the matrix such as Fe-oxides and/or in the form of void filling minerals

Figure 2. Micrographs of dolomitic rock samples. (a) sample C1; (b) sample C-02; (c) sample D-01; (d) sample E-dol; (e) sample G-01; (f) sample I-01 (all images are under XPOL, except 2a, PPL).

4.2.2 Archaeological samples

The mortar analysis was focused on features of the lime lumps. The mortars of all the archaeological building phases are characterized by the presence of binder related particles (BRP) both overburnt, underburnt and lime lumps *sensu strictu* [7].

The Carolingian mortars show a large number of BRPs as underburnt fragments of dolomitic rocks that retain texture and unreacted minerals such as quartz (figure 3a). These underburnt fragments commonly show reaction edges. Lime lumps *sensu strictu* sometimes display anisotropic rounded, radial phases with spherulitic textures 100-250 microns large (figure 3b); under XPOL they show a roundish rosette-like shape with radial growth. These particular features may also be present as fractures or pores fillings. Their presence is quite common in dolomitic lime, and they can be interpreted as hydromagnesite or Mg-correlated phases [18]. In the fragments belonging to the Planta Tower (built during the Ottonian period) many lime lumps *sensu strictu*, and underburnt fragments were found; some of them are very rich in polycrystalline quartz (figure 3c-c1).

The building phases from the 11-12th centuries show two different type of mortars. In the first period (Early Romanesque) there are many overburnt fragments (figure 3d) whilst the underburnt are very rare. Few lime lumps *sensu strictu* with melted siliceous phases can be distinguished (figure 3e).

On the contrary, in the samples attributed to the Late Romanesque building phase, a large majority of underburnt fragments was found. Sometimes siliceous phases are visible within lime lumps, but it is not clear where they originate from (original raw materials or mixed with the binder during mortar preparation).

Similarly, in the Gothic samples, it is possible to distinguish different underburnt rock textures. Spherulite shaped crystals were formed within lumps, possibly related to high Mg amount in the raw material or to specific conservative conditions of the mortars.

Figure 3. Micrographs of the binder of archaeological samples. a) underburnt rock fragment (XPOL); b) textural features related with the presence of hydromagnesite (XPOL); c-c1) lime lump with unreacted quartz (PPL and XPOL respectively); d) overburnt vitrified (amorphous) BRP, formed in the hottest areas of the kiln where the temperatures reached were sufficient to start melting the carbonate phases. Some quartz grains are clearly visible inside the lump matrix. -(XPOL); e) lime lump with partially melted siliceous phases.

4.3 Lime kiln locations in relation to potential quarrying sites

The toponym *chalchera* is found four times in the Val Müstair. Their location is shown in figure 1. Site C1 (Prà Chalchera – Lime kiln meadow) lies in the village of Tschier, at the foot of a large scree slope below a dolomitic rock outcrop close to the pass dal Fuorn. C2 marks a dolomitic outcrop near the village of Lü with the name “crippel de la chalchera” – cliff of the lime-kiln. In two cases the “chalchera” toponyms (C3 and C4) are located in the bottom of the valley next to a water course, with no dolomitic outcrops nearby.

The geographic distribution of the toponym *chalchera*, which indicates the former presence of lime kilns, shows that they were erected close to the material sources, and that different ways of collecting carbonate rocks were used. Apart from rocky outcrops, from which stones had to be quarried, scree slopes and riverbeds were used as a source of dolomitic material. This has important implications for the provenancing of the materials, since dolomitic rocks collected from riverbeds could have originated from different sites along the river’s course. A batch of lime coming from a kiln and used in mortar production could therefore include materials from different sources.

The fact that the lime kilns were located close to the sources of material is economic, as lime has a smaller density than the carbonate minerals used in its production and is therefore easier to transport. The toponyms give no indication as to the age of the kilns; it is therefore not possible to say if the kiln sites were in contemporary use, or if the mode of collection of raw materials changed over time.

5. Discussion and conclusions

The lime binder of the mortar samples from the monastery of St. John from the different periods is composed of mineralogical phases characteristic of dolomitic binders with the exception of the archaeological sample of the Late Romanesque period. This confirms the strong relationship with the geological resources of the area.

The textural analysis of the dolomitic rock samples demonstrated that the same typological groups exhibit different textural characteristics. This is not only true for the lithological variability of pebbles and gravels collected in the Val Vau river bed but also for the remaining groups. In addition, the individual samples may show marked heterogeneity of the dolomite crystal size, morphology, boundary of the crystals, replacement of bioclasts, void filling minerals. Results clearly show that there is not a specific texture for each group. Therefore, the affinity between the textural features of the raw materials and that of the underburnt fragments in the lime lumps cannot be used as criterion for a univocal correlation.

More promising is the mineralogical composition of the samples analysed. The rocks belonging to the D and I groups show not negligible amounts of quartz in the form of void filling mineral. Unreacted quartz (and most probably mica muscovite) was detected in the sample from the Ottonian period suggesting the provenance from outcrops from the Early-Middle Triassic dolomite rock formation in the northern sector of Müstair valley. Quartz was also detected in underburnt fragments of the Carolingian and Early Romanesque period suggesting similar procurement areas. For the remaining archaeological mortars (Gothic and Late Romanesque), provenance cannot be inferred, even if quartz was found associated with lime lumps from the Romanesque period.

The analytical evidence finds additional motivation from the close vicinity of I outcrops with the local toponym indicating a lime-kiln near Lü village (c2 location in figure 1).

A complementary approach using geochemistry of major, minor and trace elements also including Rare Earths Elements (REEs), both of the geological and archaeological samples using (Laser Ablation) ICP-MS, will be the next step of the research as suggested in other scientific research [19-21]. Finally, the petrographic application to raw materials sourcing will be further investigated including a major number of archaeological samples. Heating trials of dolomitic rocks will be carried out to control the modification induced during the technological process of dolomitic lime manufacturing.

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